

Do parents have worse health? A comparison of people in same-sex and different-sex relationships

Yuxuan Jin^{1,2} and Deni Mazrekaj^{2,3,4}

1. Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute (NIDI) - KNAW/University of Groningen, Lange Houtstraat 19, 2511 CV, Den Haag, the Netherlands
2. Department of Sociology, Utrecht University, Padualaan 14, 3584 CH, Utrecht, the Netherlands
3. Nuffield College, University of Oxford, New Road, OX1 1NF, Oxford, UK
4. Leuven Economics of Education Research, KU Leuven, Naamsestraat 69, 3000, Leuven, Belgium

Summary

1. We examine whether the association between parenthood and health differs between people in same-sex and different-sex relationships.
 2. We find that parents, on average, are less likely to experience heavy episodic drinking than non-parents, but are just as likely to smoke; in contrast with some prior studies, no differences are found between parents and non-parents in self-rated health, physical health, and mental health.
 3. The association between parenthood and health does not differ between people in same-sex and different-sex relationships.
 4. Policymakers can implement social policies that aim at reducing childbearing-related stress to foster a supportive environment for parents and enhance public health outcomes.
 5. Policymakers can help individuals who intend to raise children, including same-sex couples, to reduce their concerns about parenting and minority stress.
 6. Policy should ensure that same-sex couples are not discriminated against in their parental rights based on health- or risky behavior-related concerns.
-

1. Introduction

Although rewarding, having a child also leads to multiple stressors, including financial difficulties, time constraints, emotional strains, and physical childcare demands. Exposure to those stressors in the long term could lead to worse mental and physical health for parents than for non-parents, such as depression and fatigue (Nelson et al., 2014; Nomaguchi & Milkie, 2020). In this policy brief, we highlight the study we recently conducted (Jin & Mazrekaj, 2024) in which we investigated (1) whether the association between parenthood and health exists, and (2) whether this potential association differs between people in same-sex and different-sex relationships.

Understanding the consequences of parenthood on the health of same-sex couples is important as same-sex couples may experience a double burden when they become parents. In addition to general parenting stressors, same-sex parents may face unique minority stressors, including legal challenges on the way to parenthood and prejudice and discrimination in their daily lives. These unique minority stressors may create a more stressful environment for people in same-sex relationships than people in different-sex relationships.

Previous research has mostly found that parenthood leads to worse health outcomes (Nomaguchi & Milkie, 2020). However, parents tend to engage in fewer risky health behaviors than non-parents: they tend to drink less alcohol and smoke less (Bricard et al., 2017; Patrick et al., 2020). One of the explanations is that parents may monitor and regulate their risky health behaviors to provide a healthier environment for their children. However, it is unclear how parenthood is associated with risky health

behaviors for people in same-sex relationships.

2. The context and the analysis

We use the Longitudinal Internet Studies for the Social Sciences (LISS) panel administered by CentERdata (Tilburg University, The Netherlands). The LISS panel is a multi-wave household survey with a nationally representative sample in the Netherlands collected between 2008 and 2021. The data include 196 people in same-sex relationships and 6,948 people in different-sex relationships.

The Dutch context provides an opportunity to compare parents and non-parents who are in same-sex or different-sex relationships. In fact, the Netherlands was the first country to legalize same-sex marriage in 2001. Same-sex couples in the Netherlands can have a child through various paths. One common way is through second-parent or joint adoption. Female same-sex couples can give birth to a child through artificial insemination. Social mothers can become legal parents at childbirth (Evertsson et al., 2020). Same-sex parents are eligible for parenting leave in most instances (Kaufman et al., 2022). In addition, the Netherlands has high public support for same-sex parenting. A national survey in 2018 showed 85% of respondents supported gay and lesbian couples having the right to adopt children (ESS, 2020).

We use linear and logistic regression models to estimate the association between parenthood and health outcomes and behaviors. We further add the interaction term between relationship type and parenthood status in the model to test whether the association between parenthood and health differs between people in same-sex and different-sex relationships. We analyze a wide range of health indicators, including

three health outcomes (self-rated health, physical health, and mental health) and two risky health behaviors (smoking and heavy episodic drinking).

3. Results

We have four key findings. First, our results show that parenthood is not associated with health outcomes. Parents and non-parents do not have significant differences in mental health, physical health, and self-rated health. The finding contrasts with our expectation that parents may have worse health outcomes than non-parents because of parenting stress.

Second, parenthood status is not associated with smoking status but is significantly associated with the reduction of the probability of experiencing heavy episodic drinking. After adding all control variables, parents are 4 percentage points less likely to experience heavy episodic drinking than non-parents. These findings contrast with our expectation that parents would both drink less alcohol and smoke less than non-parents as they regulate their health behaviors on purpose to provide a healthier environment for their children. A possible explanation is that drinking alcohol is more likely to be public and involves other people compared to smoking.

The third key finding is that the associations between parenthood and three health outcomes do not significantly differ between people in same-sex and different-sex relationships. This finding is not in line with the idea that people in same-sex relationships may experience more negative consequences of parenthood on health outcomes than people in different-sex relationships because of a double burden from general parenting stress and unique minority stress.

Lastly, we find that the associations between parenthood status and two risky health behaviors (smoking and heavy episodic drinking) also do not significantly differ between same-sex and different-sex relationships.

4. Policy recommendations

Our findings have important implications for society and policy on parenthood, health, and same-sex couples.

First, **policymakers can implement social policies that aim at reducing childbearing-related stress** to foster a supportive environment for parents and enhance public health outcomes. Our results show that being a parent is likely not a very harmful event for parental health no matter if you are in a same-sex or different-sex relationship in the Netherlands. This may be due to the relatively generous family policies in countries like the Netherlands, which help mitigate the stress of childbearing. Our study underscores the potential for family-oriented welfare policies to improve parental well-being.

Second, **policymakers can help individuals who intend to raise children, including same-sex couples, to reduce their concerns about parenting and minority stress.** This could be achieved by working closely with practitioners and clinicians and incorporating these issues into upper secondary education in an inclusive manner. Additionally, policymakers can promote awareness through family planning services and other parenting advice programs.

Moreover, **policy should ensure that same-sex couples are not discriminated against in their parental rights based on health- or risky behavior-related concerns.** At the national level, legal barriers should be

dismantled if they exist. At the European level, institutions should facilitate knowledge sharing to help Member States in their efforts to remove these barriers. In some countries, such as Hungary and Poland, same-sex couples are not allowed to adopt children. A common claim by those opponents of same-sex parental rights is to question the ability of same-sex parents to raise a child successfully. Our study shows same-sex parents are able to take care of their children well. Same-sex couples appear to have a similar ability to cope with parenting challenges as different-sex couples.

Finally, **policymakers can raise public awareness of the rights of same-sex parents** and create a supportive environment where same-sex parents and their children face less stigma and discrimination. The context could be important for parents' health for people in same-sex relationships. In addition to the policy support for over twenty years, the Netherlands has a very high percentage of people who are in favor of the parental rights of same-sex couples.

What is EFFect ?

EFFect is an impact-driven research project aiming to enhance the quality of education in the EU by providing evidence-based policy recommendations and conducting rigorous research on the education policies of individual EU member states.

References

Bricard, D., Legleye, S., & Khlal, M. (2017). Changes in Smoking Behavior over Family Transitions: Evidence for Anticipation and Adaptation Effects. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 14(6), Article 6. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph14060610>

ESS Round 10: European Social Survey Round 10 Data. (2020). *Data file edition 3.0. Sikt—Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research, Norway - Data Archive and distributor of ESS data for ESS ERIC*. [Dataset].

<https://doi.org/10.21338/NSD-ESS10-2020>

Evertsson, M., Jaspers, E., & Moberg, Y. (2020). Parentalization of same-sex couples: Family formation and leave rights in five Northern European countries. *The Palgrave Handbook of Family Policy*, 397–428.

Kaufman, G., Auðardóttir, A. M., Mazrekaj, D., Pettigrew, R. N., Stambolis-Ruhstorfer, M., Juros, T. V., & Yerkes, M. A. (2022). Are parenting leaves available for LGBTQ parents? Examining policies in Canada, Croatia, France, Iceland, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom. In *Research handbook on leave policy* (pp. 325–337). Edward Elgar Publishing.

<https://www.elgaronline.com/edcollchap/book/9781800372214/book-part-9781800372214-35.xml>

Nelson, S. K., Kushlev, K., & Lyubomirsky, S. (2014). The pains and pleasures of parenting: When, why, and how is parenthood associated with more or less well-being? *Psychological Bulletin*, 140(3), 846–895. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0035444>

Nomaguchi, K., & Milkie, M. A. (2020). Parenthood and Well-Being: A Decade in

Review. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 82(1), 198–223. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jomf.12646>

Patrick, M. E., Evans-Polce, R., Wagner, A. C., & Mehus, C. J. (2020). High-intensity drinking by parental status: Differences by age and sex. *Addictive Behaviors*, 102, 106180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addbeh.2019.106180>

Further Information:

Jin, Y., & Mazrekaj, D. (2024). The association between parenthood and health: A comparison of people in same-sex and different-sex relationships. *SSM - Population Health*, 26, 101685. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssmph.2024.101685>